

Electron Impact Induced Fragmentation of Schiff Bases of 2-hydroxy-5-methylbenzaldehyde

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Mass spectral fragmentation of Schiff bases derived from 2-hydroxy-5-methylbenzaldehyde and arylamines as well as benzylamine are reported. Six-centre H-transfer McLafferty rearrangement, HCN elimination from M⁺ as well as from the other fragments and formation of a benzisoxazole cation are the common features of the mass spectra. Arylamines Schiff bases show M⁺ as the base peaks while benzylamine Schiff base gives m/e 91, tropylium ion, as the base peak.

MASS spectral studies of Schiff bases have not been reported before 1966. Since then also, the subject has not been thoroughly investigated; particularly Schiff bases of 2-hydroxyarylaldehydes have not been given due attention. *ortho*-Substituent is known to exert a profound effect on the mode of fragmentation of aromatic compounds. In light of these facts, in course of our studies on Schiff bases, it was considered interesting to study the mass spectral fragmentation of a few Schiff bases of 2-hydroxy-5-methylbenzaldehyde¹⁻⁵.

Initial ionization always occurred on the N-atom giving iminium ion. Parallel to the ordinary Schiff bases¹, these compounds gave stable molecular ions (M⁺) and the M⁺ was the base peak in the spectra when the anils were derived from aromatic amines (i.e. 1-4). Benzylamine Schiff base 5, gave an intense M⁺ peak but it was not the base peak. The base peak was at m/e 91, which corresponded to tropylium ion¹⁰ formed by α -cleavage. The unusual stability and facility of the formation of this ion might be the reason of the high intensity of this peak. Compounds 1-4 were observed to cleave at either end of the azomethine (-CH=N-) linkage to give major fragments (6 and 7) which decomposed further by the ejection of HCN to daughter ions (8 and 9). These second generation ions can also be formed directly from the molecular ions (Scheme 1). 2 showed some diversion due to 4-CH₃ group. It also gave significant tropylium ion at m/e 91, which was formed from the ion 7 formed through α -cleavage (7-10). The peak at m/e 91 was second in intensity to the base peak M⁺. Stability of the molecular ions was also reflected in the

Scheme-1

Scheme-2

Six-centre transfer of -H McLafferty Rearrangement

Scheme-3

1. R = -Ph
2. R = -C₆H₄-4-OH₃
3. R = -C₆H₄-4-OCH₃
4. R = -C₆H₄-4-NO₂
5. R = -CH₂-C₆H₅

observation that from the ions substituents on the N-phenyl moiety either were ejected as such or ejected as typical neutral particles from them, e.g. 3 showed (M - OCH₃) and (M - CHO) peaks, while, 4 showed (M - NO), (M - CO) and (M - NO₂) peaks. Besides the M⁺, all the compounds showed (M - 1) peaks nearly equally strong, formed by the loss of the azomethine H⁺ and (M - 2) of low intensity. All the compounds showed (M + 1) peaks⁹ of variable intensities, probably due to the ions formed by the intermolecular H-capture by the molecular ions.

Skeletal rearrangements of the type [ABC]⁺ → [AC]⁺ + B are common features of the compounds of the type Ar - X = Y - Ar'⁹⁻¹¹. 1-5 showed elimination of HCN (M - HCN) through a similar rearrangement process⁹. Participation of *ortho*-OH group was obvious in these processes and 1-4 gave a dibenzofuran ion 11. Through similar mechanism, 5 gave a dibenzopyran ion 12 at m/e 196. Another interesting case of similar participation was observed in the formation of 16 at m/e 119 and 15

at m/e 106. These ions could be formed through a six-centre H-transfer from -OH to imminium ion by a McLafferty rearrangement. 15 and 16 may undergo elimination of CO to form ions m/e 78 and m/e 91, respectively. Peak at m/e 91 of variable intensity in all the spectra could thus be accounted for. The peak at m/e 134 in all the spectra was attributed to benzisoxazole ion 17 which was stabilized by resonance. 17 could be formed by the participation of the *o*-OH group in the isoxazole ring formation with concomitant loss of the N-aryl radical (Scheme 4). As benzisoxazole type ions are less stabilized than the corresponding benzoxazole ions¹, intensity of the peak at m/e 134 was never more than 50%. 5 was observed to fragment by a different route through ion 18 (M - Ph) to form ion at m/e 121 by the ejection of HCN.

The Schiff bases were prepared by the reaction of equimolar amounts of the appropriate amines with 2-hydroxy-5-methylbenzaldehyde. The bases were crystallized from ethanol.

The mass spectra were recorded on a Varian Mat-112 S Mass spectrometer at 70 eV energy.

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